

Exploring Application of LLMs and AI-based Models in Addressing EDI Concerns

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Abstract. Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) challenges in the educational domain include various areas that require attention and improvement by educators, researchers, and policymakers. EDI within the educational context focuses on eliminating structural barriers, facilitating access to high-quality education, nurturing inclusive learning environments, and addressing the needs for special education and disabilities. Notably, students with disabilities encounter unique challenges that warrant careful consideration in EDI discussions. With the integration of cutting-edge AI technologies into the educational domain, there are significant opportunities to address EDI concerns. However, it is crucial to be mindful of the potential repercussions these AI tools could have on students' learning experiences. In this study, we propose a model that integrates ChatGPT with the Hugging Face, Using the Hugging-GPT framework to offer advanced features such as enhanced knowledge integration and multi-modal input processing. This system facilitates a seamless integration of different existing AI models and leverages the power of LLMs to help address diverse student needs in the educational domain and provide a positive learning experience, especially for students with disabilities.

Keywords: EDI · Large Language Models (LLMs) · Education.

1 Introduction

The educational domain faces various EDI challenges that require attention and improvement across different areas, such as providing inclusive learning environments and addressing the needs for special education and disabilities. With the ongoing integration of AI technologies into the educational domain, substantial opportunities arise to address EDI concerns. However, it is crucial to be mindful of the potential repercussions these AI tools may have on students' learning experiences [2]. This study will specifically explore the application of ChatGPT, an advanced language model created by OpenAI, in education. The aim is to shed light on the advantages and disadvantages of integrating AI technologies, particularly ChatGPT, while addressing concerns related to EDI.

By creating inclusive learning environments that cater to the diverse needs of all students, we aim to promote equal opportunities, respect, and fair treatment, regardless of individuals' backgrounds, identities, or abilities. EDI within the educational context focuses on eliminating structural barriers, facilitating access to high-quality education, and nurturing inclusive learning environments. This involves addressing issues related to students' sense of belonging, ethnicity, race, and disabilities throughout their educational journey. Notably, students with disabilities encounter unique challenges that warrant careful consideration in EDI discussions [3]. Some of these challenges include:

- Sense of Belonging: Due to possible stigmatization, discrimination, or a lack of inclusive practices, students with disabilities may find it difficult to feel a sense of belonging within the educational community. This could have a detrimental effect on their motivation, engagement, and general well-being.
- Inclusive and customized learning opportunities: In order for students with disabilities to be successful in their academic journey, it is highly important to provide them with specialized resources and assistance. This includes access to tutoring services, specialized learning materials, and educators who possess the necessary skills to address their needs. However, limited access to such resources can lead to unequal educational opportunities for students with disabilities. It is important to address these gaps and ensure that all students have equal access to the resources they require to have a positive learning experience. [4].

AI-based technologies have the potential to greatly assist students with disabilities in their educational pursuits. Here are a few ways in which AI can contribute to EDI efforts:

- Adaptive learning platforms: learning that is tailored to the needs of each individual student, including those with disabilities, is made possible by AI-powered adaptive learning platforms. This tailored strategy can encourage participation and improve academic performance, particularly for students with disabilities.
- Tools for accessibility: AI-based technologies can automatically produce learning materials that are accessible, such as closed captions for videos and the generation of alt text for images. These tools aid in making educational material accessible to students who have cognitive, visual, or auditory impairments.
- Inclusive communication: By providing text-to-speech and speech-to-text functionality, AI-powered language models like ChatGPT can promote inclusive communication. As a result, students with hearing or speech impairments can interact with their peers and teachers and actively participate in class discussions.

By utilizing the potential of AI technologies, educators and policymakers can create inclusive learning environments that effectively address the diverse challenges faced by students with disabilities. To ensure equity, it is crucial to

critically assess the ethical issues, potential biases, and privacy issues related to the integration of AI, including the use of ChatGPT.

In this work, we propose adopting a framework called HuggingGPT, which combines the strength of ChatGPT with external models from the Hugging Face community to help address EDI concerns, as elaborated in the following section.

2 Methodology

This study explores how the application of AI-based technologies, such as Transformer agents from HuggingFace (a well-known repository of NLP models), affects student learning and EDI in a classroom setting. LLMs are strong models that are excellent at responding to queries with input in natural language. Transformer agents, when added to LLMs, are unique in that they can reason and think through a process in several steps, which enables them to weigh various factors and incorporate different tools into their decision-making. We can improve natural language understanding by combining Transformer agents with LLMs.

These agents allow us to ask questions, and if LLMs are unable to respond right away, they can use a variety of tools at their disposal to investigate the matter further and offer thorough explanations.

In order to handle complicated AI tasks, LLMs should be able to coordinate with external models to utilize their powers.

As shown in Fig. 1, LLMs (like ChatGPT) use language as an interface to connect various AI models (like those in Hugging Face) in order to solve challenging AI tasks. An LLM serves as a controller in this concept, organizing and managing the collaboration of expert models. According to the user's request, the LLM first plans a list of tasks, after which it assigns expert models for each task. The LLM compiles the findings and responds to the user. After the tasks have been completed by the expert models.

HuggingGPT, a system that acts as a link between Hugging Face, the machine learning (ML) community, and LLMs, such as ChatGPT, will be used in our proposed model. With the help of this system, we will be able to process input from various modalities and take on challenging AI tasks by utilizing the abilities of LLMs and the wide variety of AI agents offered by Hugging Face. The HuggingGPT integration entails connecting to ChatGPT and integrating the model descriptions of various AI models found in the Hugging Face library into the prompt. Through this fusion, ChatGPT is able to access the knowledge of these models and make use of it to produce answers to user questions. Some of these features are listed below [1]:

- Task Planning: Using ChatGPT, it breaks down user requests into possible tasks that can be completed with prompts after understanding the users' intentions.
- Model Selection: Based on model descriptions, ChatGPT chooses professional models hosted on Hugging Face to complete the planned tasks.

Fig. 1. High-level architecture of the model [1]

- Task Execution: It calls and runs each chosen model, then send the outcomes to ChatGPT.
- Response Generation: Finally, integrating all model predictions into ChatGPT to produce user-friendly responses.

Through the use of HuggingGPT, we can tap into the collective knowledge and capabilities of LLMs and the ML community to address complex AI tasks and provide informative responses to user inquiries. This system facilitates a seamless integration of different AI models and leverages the power of LLMs to help address diverse student needs in the educational domain and provide a positive learning experience, especially for students with disabilities.

Let's take the example of a disabled student who finds it difficult to take notes in class. HuggingGPT's capabilities for speech-to-text conversion and image processing can be used to help solve this problem.

The student can use the system to convert spoken material in the classroom into text by using the HuggingGPT framework. The HuggingGPT agent can be used by the student to input audio recordings of lectures or group discussions. The agent will then use its language-understanding capabilities to convert the spoken content into text format. The student can then quickly access the transcription and review it, using detailed notes to support their understanding of the course material.

The disabled student can access lecture notes and record crucial information from them by using HuggingGPT for speech-to-text conversion and image analysis. For those who struggle with conventional note-taking techniques, this feature offers a useful tool. This use-case also demonstrates the potential of AI tools like HuggingGPT to close the gap and give disabled students the same opportunities as other students to participate and learn effectively in the classroom.

- Image generation from text can greatly benefit disabled students in multiple ways. It offers an alternative means of comprehension for visually impaired

students, granting access to information through visual representations. This enhances their learning experience and fosters inclusion. Additionally, students with cognitive disabilities or learning difficulties can benefit from simplified information in images, aiding comprehension and retention of complex concepts. Moreover, image generation allows students with language-based disabilities to express their thoughts and understanding through visuals, offering a more accessible and intuitive form of communication.

In Fig. 2, the HuggingFace agent demonstrates image generation from text ("generate an image of a classroom"). It employs a model selection process, as part of the high-level architecture, to choose an image generation tool. This selected tool is then utilized to create the image, which is subsequently passed to the LLM for retrieval and presentation to the user.

Fig. 2. Example Image Generation code run on HuggingGPT

Fig. 3. Example Caption the Image code run on HuggingGPT

- Image captioning is highly advantageous for disabled students in multiple ways. It provides visually impaired students with descriptive captions for images, enabling comprehension and engagement with visual content. Furthermore, it fosters inclusive learning, allowing active participation in discussions and assignments related to visuals. Image captioning also promotes independent learning, empowering disabled students to interpret images without constant assistance, ensuring equal opportunities for academic success.

In Fig. 3, the HuggingFace agent's practical application showcases its ability to generate textual captions for images.

- Text-to-speech technology greatly benefits disabled students, enhancing accessibility and inclusion in education. It converts written text into spoken words, aiding visually impaired students in comprehending learning materials. Additionally, it supports students with reading difficulties or disabilities, enabling them to listen at their own pace and reinforce understanding. Text-to-speech also eases the burden on physically disabled students, ensuring

equal access to information and promoting active and independent participation in their educational journey.

Fig. 4 illustrates a visual demonstration showcasing the utilization of the HuggingFace agent for text-to-speech conversion

- Querying a document file using HuggingGPT can be immensely beneficial for disabled students. By leveraging the power of natural language processing, it enables students to pose questions and extract relevant information from the document, regardless of their physical or cognitive limitations. This technology eliminates barriers to accessing and understanding complex textual information, empowering students with disabilities to independently navigate and comprehend educational materials. With HuggingGPT’s assistance, disabled students can actively engage in research, assignments, and knowledge acquisition, fostering inclusion and equal participation in academic pursuits.

In Figure 5, we can observe the HuggingFace agent in action, utilizing it to make inquiries ("In the following ‘document‘, Where is the location of the TRRF Scientific Advisory Council Meeting?") about the information contained within a document, irrespective of the specific question asked.

Fig. 4. Example text to speech run on HuggingGPT

Fig. 5. Example querying an image or document run on HuggingGPT

3 Discussion and Future work

In this study, we proposed an AI-based model for addressing EDI concerns in education. The model integrates ChatGPT (as the controller layer) with Hugging Face (as the model layer) to offer the following features:

- Enhanced Knowledge Integration: HuggingGPT incorporates model descriptions of various AI models from the Hugging Face library into the prompt, enabling access to a wider variety of data and improving response quality and precision.
- Multimodal Input Processing: HuggingGPT can handle complex AI tasks involving text, images, or other data types, allowing interaction in diverse modalities.
- Improved Response Quality: Leveraging LLMs as HuggingGPT's "brain" enhances language comprehension and reasoning, resulting in a more tailored and higher-quality responses to the user queries.
- Seamless Integration of AI Models: HuggingGPT seamlessly integrates multiple AI models from the Hugging Face library, facilitating easy testing and comparison within a unified framework.

Fig. 6. Sample Models accessible via HuggingGPT

Although the HuggingGPT framework offers promising benefits, there are some potential drawbacks to be aware of:

- Ethical Concerns: Utilizing cutting-edge AI models like ChatGPT may inadvertently lead to inappropriate outcomes or perpetuate biases from training data. Responsible and ethical use requires continuous monitoring of biases and proactive measures to minimize them.

- Over reliance on AI: Exclusively relying on AI for educational tasks may undervalue human interaction and knowledge. Striking a balance between AI advantages and human involvement ensures AI enhances, but not replaces, human capabilities.
- Privacy and Data Security: HuggingGPT and similar frameworks necessitate processing user inputs and storing data. Protecting individuals’ sensitive data and maintaining their trust demand robust data privacy measures and security protocols.

In the future, our research aims to explore students’ specific needs and challenges related to EDI, considering factors like ethnicity, race, and disability. We will design and prototype an HuggingGPT-based system that caters to these diverse educational requirements. This future work involves:

- Inclusive System Design: Our focus is on designing an inclusive system that considers students’ diverse needs, incorporating accessibility features, cultural sensitivity, and personalized learning strategies.
- User Testing and Prototyping: Testing the system’s suitability for students facing EDI difficulties, incorporating user feedback to enhance usability in real educational contexts.
- Cost-effective AI adoption options for educational institutions in low-income areas include open-source frameworks, cloud-based services, compact language models, and collaborative partnerships.

In summary, the goal of future research direction is to contribute to the creation of an inclusive and successful AI-powered educational system that supports students with a variety of needs and encourages equity, diversity, and inclusion in the educational domain.

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